

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

Deliverable 1.3 Review of the ETIP / IWG9

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This is a Horizon Europe project (Coordination and Support Action) funded by the European Union for 3 years (from 1 July 2022 until 30 June 2025).

Project summary

Support Stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9.

The overarching goal of this project is to bring together and further develop a strong inclusive network of CCUS stakeholders – effectively interconnecting and coordinating the activities of CCUS European Technology Innovation Platforms (ETIP ZEP) and the CCUS SET Plan Implementation Plan Working Group (IWG9) – to support the development and implementation of the SET Plan.

Supporting the alignment and efficient coordination of stakeholders – including industry, researchers, public authorities, and civil society – to accelerate the delivery of the CCUS research and innovation (R&I) activities and to progress the emerging policy priorities at the EU and national level for the implementation of CCUS, will be crucial over the coming years for Europe to reach the ambitious climate targets for 2030 and 2050.

This will be achieved by efficiently aligning and coordinating the activities of ETIP ZEP and the IWG9 in a joint work programme; establishing networks and other fora to enable the stakeholders to collaborate and coordinate effectively, pooling expertise, experience and resources to address common challenges; engaging also with other programmes and external stakeholders; facilitating engagement and creating greater interaction and cohesion between the different CCUS activities; supporting the CCUS community to develop clear strategies and recommendations; accompanied by a strong continuous programme for outreach, dissemination and communication.

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1 INTRODUCTION

This deliverable aims to do a review of the Zero Emissions Platform ETIP and the Implementation Working Group 9 and to identify opportunities to improve its further impact.

The SET-Plan Implementation Plan Working Group 9 on CCUS (IWG9) is one of the ten actions of the European Strategic Energy Technology Plan (SET-Plan), which aims to accelerate the deployment of low-carbon technologies, improve new technologies and bring down costs by coordinating national research efforts. The SET Plan aims to achieve the EU's energy and climate goals and make Europe a global leader in clean energy and energy efficiency technologies. The plan does this by helping to coordinate national research and innovation (R&I) activities in developing low-carbon energy among EU Member States and 4 associated countries (Norway, Iceland, Turkey and Switzerland) and by aligning national R&I programmes with its agenda. The SET Plan steps up cooperation between governments, industry and research institutes to leverage the use of R&I funding schemes for clean energy.

The Zero Emissions Platform (ZEP) is a European Technology and Innovation Platform under the EU's SET-Plan and technical adviser to the European Commission on carbon capture and storage (CCS) and carbon capture and utilisation (CCU).

The current grant combines two support mechanisms for the CCS/CCU sector so that the support and coordination of both the ETIP and IWG9 are in the hands of one consortium. In this case, the Carbon Capture & Storage Association (CCSA) and SINTEF are responsible for executing the grant.

2 ZEP STRUCTURE REVIEW

In 2023 the ZEP embarked on a thorough review of the current structure. There has been a large increase in announced CCS and CCU projects and policy initiatives since the publication of the European Green Deal Communication in 2019. As the organisation has grown from a technical advisor on CCS and CCU to a platform that covers both technical and policy advice, the current format as an ETIP limits its range of activities and entails decreasing funding from the Horizon Europe grant. This is also why ZEP, with increasing membership funding, has added activities directly funded by its members.

Given the reduced EU grant funding and increased list of activities, the Temporary Working Group on the ZEP Future Structure prepared a plan, in addition to the recently increased membership funding; to grow the platform's role as a cornerstone for the CCS and CCU community in Europe. The considered options included further expanding its funding streams and either building up its staff or potentially joining forces with an industry association. The status quo was not considered sustainable in its current form, ZEP would not have the resources to cater for the large-scale deployment of CCS and CCU in Europe at the level needed.

The regained momentum for CCS and CCU through, for instance, the Net Zero Industry Act proposal and the drive from the European Commission, EEA countries and private and public organisations raise the question of how ZEP should be developed to operate under and drive the large-scale development

needed and become a powerful vehicle for enabling climate neutrality by 2050, and the intermediate steps in 2030 and 2040, in the most effective way.

In October and December 2023, ZEP members reviewed the various options on the table (maintaining the status quo, strengthening their organisation or joining forces with an existing trade association). They unanimously decided to go for the second route: strengthening ZEP as a membership organisation that may apply for the grant itself – in case the Commission decides to continue the ETIPs and the SET Plan. ZEP also updated its structure accordingly. Schematically, the new structure looks like this:

ETIP ZEP focuses on the technical work and supports R&I priorities, including related communication and advocacy work. ZEP-C serves as a vehicle to gather sponsorship fees from ZEP [members](#) to support and enhance the work undertaken under the ETIP ZEP by additional advocacy activities. All advocacy activities funded by ZEP-C are fact- and science-based and designed to disseminate the positions and work prepared in the ETIP to enhance ZEP’s balanced input to policy processes.

ZEP membership will continue as it currently works, with the addition of industry associations being allowed to become ZEP members. From 2024, ZEP-Communications ASBL (ZEP-C) has hired staff directly to deliver activities funded by member sponsorships, including deliverables that are additional or complementary to those covered by the grant, and applying for grants. As the ZEP membership increases, the ZEP leadership in the form of AC and ACEC can continue staffing up the secretariat to deliver its work programme and increase its impact.

The ZEP Chair has interviewed majority of ZEP members on the positioning and structure of the organisation, and how they would like to see ZEP engage with its members. Several strategic questions have been considered, for instance, whether the ZEP primarily is an ETIP or if is a membership-based association with an ETIP as its core activity/foundation. A possible change of the name of the platform is being considered but not right now – this would be for 2025 or later. Furthermore, an advocacy plan

is being developed that will be executed by the new Policy and Advocacy Director who is hired directly by the ZEP Communications ASBL. These and other items have been discussed at the latest (annual) ‘ACEC Away Day’ on 7 February 2024, with most of the ACEC members present.

Advantages:

- Building a well-established and respected organisation into a new resilient version of itself that can robustly endure gaps between grants and become sustainable in the long term.
- Increased flexibility to go beyond the technical work of an ETIP, delivering on the strengthened communications and advocacy programme to improve the impact and visibility of ZEP.
- ZEP’s brand will strengthen, along with the possibility to provide input to policymakers as an ETIP ZEP on technical areas and offering a wider range of advice as a broad stakeholder platform on different topics and effectively developing/expanding its advocacy activities. As a result, the policymakers will receive a wider range of high-quality input that is still informed by the same principles – fact- and science-based.
- Strengthening ZEP, a well-established and respected organisation, would also lead to less fragmentation among CCS organisations in Brussels, and easier and more focused engagement by stakeholders. Increased independence to set its policy work programme, which is complementary to that under the Horizon Europe grant.

Challenges:

- The ZEP Communications ASBL has started hiring its own staff, which modifies the ZEP structure and builds somewhat more complex governance system where the CCSA staff (partly or fully) funded by the grant and the ZEP-C staff work together. However, given that the CCSA cannot provide services beyond grant funding and in view of the increasing work activities caused by the ongoing CCUS deployment in Europe, this form of organisation is the feasible way forward.

3 IWG9 AND REVIEW OF THE SET PLAN IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

In the previous chapter, the IWG9 was mentioned at several occasions. This section describes further the review process of the R&I activities that will take place in 2024 and will be one of the main deliverables of this part of the grant.

As the website¹ of the SET Plan stipulates, this platform *“is a key stepping-stone to boost the transition towards a climate-neutral energy system through the development of low-carbon technologies in a fast and cost-competitive way. (...) It became one of the main instruments of the energy union’s 5th pillar on research, innovation and competitiveness. By improving new technologies and bringing down their costs through coordinated national research efforts, the SET Plan helps promote cooperation among EU countries, companies and research institutions. It does so by helping to coordinate national research and innovation activities in developing low-carbon energy among EU countries and associated countries, as well as aligning national research and innovation programmes with its agenda.”*

¹ https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/research-and-technology/strategic-energy-technology-plan_en

The Communication on the revision of the Strategic Energy Technology Plan, adopted on 20 October 2023, will help harmonise the original SET Plan strategic objectives with the European Green Deal, REPowerEU and the Green Deal Industrial Plan, notably the Net-Zero Industry Act. It aims to ensure a unified approach towards achieving Europe’s decarbonisation goals, supporting European strategic net-zero energy technologies, and building a sustainable and resilient energy future. Cross-cutting issues identified, include the following:

- Digitalisation;
- Societal needs;
- Upskilling and reskilling of the workforce;
- Acceleration of the market uptake of R&I results; and
- Improved access to funding, in particular, to scale up innovations.

The CCUS SET-Plan aims to accelerate the transition through greater coordination – EU, national, industrial, and academic research. The CCUS SET Plan Implementation Plan (IWG9) is chaired by Norway, the Netherlands, and ZEP. It has established ambitious 2030 targets and R&I activities. The work covers all parts of the CCUS value chain, including hydrogen and CDR. Recent work includes the UCL review of CCS/CCU in EU decarbonisation. The work will focus on updated CCUS targets for 2030 to deliver the EU’s higher climate ambitions, including 50 million tonnes of CO₂ per annum abated by CCS in 2030 and the availability of 25 operational commercial-scale CCS projects. The CCUS SET Plan 2030 targets can be found hereafter:

The plan is to work on the following items:

- an update of IWG9 targets and reporting on progress towards new targets;
- the facilitation of knowledge-sharing priorities between participating countries; and
- the facilitation of contributions of stakeholders, including from ZEP and the IWG9.

Terms of Reference and a Temporary Working Group will be set up in Q1 2024 (see terms of reference for the workstream dedicated to “Full-scale projects, clusters and infrastructure” under section 6). New IWG9 targets and associated R&I actions will be drafted and an update will be

provided at the ZEP AC/IWG9 Plenaries in March and June 2024. The new IWG9 targets and associated R&I actions will be finalised in Q4 2024 and approved at the ZEP AC/IWG9 plenary in December 2024. Originally, this work item was supposed to be completed by June 2024 but the review is taking more time than anticipated.

The review of the targets and activities is conducted via 4 workstreams:

- Full-scale projects, clusters and infrastructure;
- CO₂ capture;
- CO₂ storage; and
- CO₂ utilisation.

Meetings took place for each of these workstreams on 24, 25, and 26 April 2024. A second meeting took place on 22 May 2024 for the workstream dedicated to CO₂ capture. Participants came from different sectors, including academia, NGOs, industry, and national government. This participation enabled different expert perspectives regarding the definition of the new targets and activities. The secretariat provided a policy oversight to reflect the ambitions of the proposed EU 2040 climate target, the Industrial Carbon Management Strategy and the upcoming regulation Net-Zero Industry Act prior to the discussions. First meetings allowed for informed feedback on the new R&I targets and activities.

At the combined ZEP AC and IWG9 General Assembly of 20 March 2024, the organisations agreed on the following procedure.

- From April to June, the IWG9 Strategic Coordination Group and four theme-specific Working Groups will continue their work to review the targets and R&I actions. Much of this work will be done in kind by the actors closely and strongly involved in the R&I side of topics such as CO₂ capture, transport and storage. There is no budget for the remuneration of the involved actors so we are dependent here on their support (which is the case)
- Much of this work will be done through existing structures such as the EERA Joint Programme on CCS and the ZEP Technology Committee. The Technology Committee gathers technical experts, including researchers, working on CCS and covers a wide range of expertise from CO₂ capture to transport and storage.
- The Secretariat is, together with the IWG9 Strategic Coordination Group, actively reaching out to European governments to get them involved in the review process – both through the IWG9 channels and the ZEP Government Group.
- In May, IWG9 member states should meet to discuss the draft updates or the secretariat will hold bilateral interviews to map the input of member states (to be decided)
- At the June 19 ZEP AC/IWG9 Plenary, the progress until then. Given the scope of the work, the full review will likely take the rest of 2024 with a final approval to be expected at the December 2024 ZEP AC/IWG9 Plenary.

As described in the table below, both the European Energy Research Alliance and the ZEP/IWG9 Technology Committee are involved in the process. This inclusion ensures that a wide range of experts specialised research topics along the CCS value chain can be included and provide their

input in the process. This work requires significant in-kind support from the workstream co-chairs to collect input and develop R&I targets and activities.

SET Plan IWG9 planning 2024												
Type of meetings/Months	Jan	Febr	March	April	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
SET Plan IWG9 meetings												
ZEP AC/IWG9 Plenary			20.mar			19.jun			11.sep			04.des
IWG9 Strategic Co-ordination Group			07.mar		10.mai			x			x	
IWG9 Working Group 2 (CO2 Capture) (IWG9 Countries)			01.mar	24.apr	22.mai			x?	x?		x	
SET Plan support from ZEP/EERA CCS												
EERA JP CCS			x		12.apr	04.jun						x
ZEP Technical Committee		22.feb			08.mai				25.sep		20.nov	

- WG1 Full scale projects, clusters and infra** (Lead: Lamberto Eldering)
- WG2 CO2 capture** (EERA JP CCS and ZEP Technology Committee. Lead: Marie Bysveen)
- WG3 CO2 storage** (EERA JP CCS and ZEP Technology Committee. Lead: Filip Neele, Jonathan Pearce)
- WG4. CO2 use** (ZEP Technology Committee. Lead: Anastasios Perimenis)
- IWG9 Strategic Coordination Group** : IWG9 Co-chairs, IWG9 WG leads, DG RTD, DG ENER (TBD)

The secretariat has produced a ‘status report’ of the CCUS 2030 targets and the R&I activities. Such an exercise was done during the previous grant period (IMPACTS92) and was a lengthy report³. However, in this grant report more capacity was available with several R&I partners involved in producing the report (a.o. CO2 Value Europe). The status report for this review will need to be done in-house and form the basis for the discussions in the various WGs.

Together with the IWG9 co-chairs, the ZEP secretariat will ensure that there is a coordination between the new targets and activities and the recently published targets of the Industrial Carbon Management Strategy, the upcoming regulation Net-Zero Industry Act as well as the proposed EU 2040 climate target. It is important to have the CCUS SET Plan targets not developed in isolation but in tandem with the latest EU policy developments and plans.

4 COMBINING THE SECRETARIATS

The most important change compared to previous grants is that the secretariats of IWG9 and ZEP are now combined. The ZEP is also the co-chair of the IWG9, together with Norway and the Netherlands, as before. The two organisations have a joint work programme, do their quarterly meetings together (the IWG9 General Assembly and the ZEP Advisory Council) and their members sit in shared Committees and Working Groups.

Benefits

The experience of ZEP and IWG9, after eighteen months in the grant period, has largely been **positive and the structure has proven to be impactful**.

² See the report CCUS Roadmap to 2030 which was published in November 2021, and includes the ten updated CCUS 2030 targets. Link to the report on the IMPACTS9 website: https://ccus-setplan.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/CCUS-SET-Plan_CCUS-Roadmap-2030.pdf
³ [Grant period July 2019 - June 2022 - IMPACTS9 \(ccus-setplan.eu\)](#)

1. Given the overlap of activities, topics, and desired outcomes, it made a lot of sense for IWG9 and ZEP to merge their structures as much as possible. As both organisations indicated in writing before the tender of the grant was published, the new grant “should preserve the strengths from both the current governance structures to engage the broadest possible group of CCUS stakeholders, but at the same time coordinate the activities to increase impact and benefits for stakeholders and efficiency.” This request certainly has been met, though coordinating activities is not enough to be impactful (see the next section on the downsides of the structure).

2. The R&I focus of IWG9 is now trickling down into ZEP workstreams and reports.

3. With just one secretariat in place, it is much easier to coordinate projects and processes. ZEP and IWG9 have been able to contribute to all focus areas of the project .4. The quarterly meetings are very useful to inform the two constituencies of the organisations at the same time about developments, plans and actions. This enforces the interaction and knowledge sharing that is fundamental to the Zero Emissions Platform.

5. The annual work programmes are considered to be living documents that can be adapted according to political developments. As an example, the ZEP/IWG9 could rapidly respond to the announcement of the Net Zero Industry Act in March 2023 and deploy advocacy activities to preserve the many legislative features of this Act that will drive the CCS ecosystem forward and accelerate the deployment of CCS projects in Europe. The governance structure is also agile, with its temporary working groups able to deliver high-quality analysis of policy, technical and market developments.

6. The Zero Emissions Platform and IWG9 have been effective at addressing and feeding into crucial policy developments, including among others the Green Deal Industrial Plan encompassing the Net Zero Industry Act, the Strategic Technologies for Europe Platform, and the Temporary Crisis and Transition Framework, the preparation of the Industrial Carbon Management Strategy the revision of the EU ETS Monitoring and Reporting Regulation, the revision of the CO₂ storage directive Guidance Documents, the Carbon Removal Certification Framework, the revision of national energy and climate plans, and the preparation of an EU climate target for 2040. The feedback in this fact-changing and extensive policy landscape consisted of policy papers, consultation responses, and webinars, among others. In addition to this policy work the Zero Emissions Platform and IWG9 provided technical input on complex matters along the CCS and CCU value chain, including by supporting the CCUS Forum report on CO₂ specifications and producing a report on CO₂ transport by ship and a report on biodiversity and land use. This twin work has provided usable input for EU and national policymakers working on CCS and CCU matters.

We can safely conclude that the combination of the two organisations under one grant works. For the next grant period, it is advised that all parties agree beforehand how much the deliverables depend on in-kind support, notably by ZEP members and co-chairs of the various committees. This should be done by the grant applicants but also discussed with ZEP members before applying for a new grant.

5 CONCLUSION

The coordinated work of ZEP and IWG9 is efficient under the current structure, even as the CCS and CCU market starts to mature, the European policy framework for CCS and CCU is being shaped and the focus shifts to deployment instead of pure R&D of the technologies.

In order to increase the future impact of ZEP and IWG9 and accelerate the development of the CCS/CCU market, it is important that the network of the two organisations continues to expand with relevant stakeholders and that the network should not only be informed proactively on policy and market developments by the secretariat, but that knowledge sharing *within* the ZEP/IWG9 network is maintained as a continuous and dynamic activity.

Such an interplay between the CC(U)S stakeholders can be observed in the current review of the SET Plan targets: through a structural coordination process of the secretariat and the IWG9 and ZEP leadership, the network of CC(U)S experts is being given the opportunity to revise the SET Plan targets in a collective effort. The ZEP/IWG9 secretariat is putting careful consideration into linking up the various policy developments into this revision process, for instance the newly adopted 50 Mt CO₂ storage target for 2030 that has now been written down in the Net-Zero Industry Act. This enables the various partners of the platform – knowledge institutions, industrial players and NGOs – to include the latest policy developments in their internal CCS/CCU work streams. The ZEP and IWG9 structures function well in the sense that they are real knowledge-sharing platforms that also prevent CCS policies from being developed in isolation by member states and third countries.

What is crucial is that support for the ETIP and the IWG9 remains in place after the current grant period ends (in June 2025). The ZEP and the IWG9 have proven their value in being the linking pin and accelerator in Europe's CCS landscape. Continued (financial) support from the European Commission is paramount to keep the current momentum and avoid fragmentation of the CCS ecosystem – both at the policy and the R&I level.

6 ANNEX

Terms of Reference – WG1 Full-scale projects, clusters and infrastructure

The European Strategic Energy Technology Plan (SET Plan) established 10 priority actions, covering a wide range of technologies, including one focused on carbon capture and storage (CCS) and carbon capture and utilisation (CCU) (action 9). Each priority action has developed an Implementation Plan which outlines clear targets, alongside the Research and Innovation (R&I) activities needed to achieve them. The progress of the Implementation Plans is monitored by Implementation Working Groups (IWG) and the IWG9 focuses on CCS/CCU. The SET Plan is expected to grow in importance in view of the upcoming Net Zero Industry Act.

The IWG9 monitors progress on CCS/CCU. In 2016, the European Commission, the SET Plan countries, and industry agreed on **10 targets** for CCS and CCU for 2030. These were updated in 2020 (link to the [past 10 targets](#)) to reflect better the direction of the sector, including the challenges ahead. To deliver on the 10 targets, IWG9 identified **8 R&I activities** (link to the [IWG9 2017 Implementation Plan](#)). The objective of this working group is to produce **new activities and targets by June 2024**.

The working group, its co-chair(s), and the related former R&I activities and targets are summarised in the table below:

WGs	Co-Chair	Work	Former R&I activities	Former R&I targets
<p>WG1 Full-scale projects, clusters and infrastructure</p>	<p>Lamberto Eldering (pending acceptance)</p>	<p>Drafting 1 document describing new R&I activities and new R&I targets</p>	<p>1. Delivery of a whole chain CCS project operating in the power sector</p> <p>2. Delivery of regional CCS and CCU clusters, including feasibility for a European hydrogen infrastructure</p> <p>3. EU Projects of Common Interest for CO2 transport infrastructure</p> <p>8. Understanding and communicating the role of CCS and CCU in meeting European and national energy and climate change goals</p>	<p>1. Delivery of 15 commercial-scale CCS projects linked to industrial CO2 sources. Further 10 projects having completed a FEED study and 5 having made an investment decision.</p> <p>2. Delivery of 10 commercial-scale CCS projects for clean, flexible power and heat generation (including waste-to-energy plants), complementary to increased renewable energy generation in the energy mix.</p> <p>3. EU member states and external SET-Plan countries having completed national and regional CCS roadmaps for the development of dedicated CO2 transport infrastructure (new, retrofitted, and repurposed), including clusters of CO2 sources and shared, cross-border CO2 infrastructure. The</p>

				<p>infrastructure being included in the European Ten-Year Network Development Plan (TYNDP).</p> <p>4. At least 10 additional EU Projects of Common Interest (PCI) for CO2 transport infrastructure, with a focus on Central, Eastern, and Southern Europe. Experience from the first full-scale CCS project should be taken into account in the SET-Plan activities linked to targets 3 and 4.</p> <p>9. By 2030, first large-scale commercial installations enabled by a supportive regulatory framework and risk-sharing financial measures at national and EU level including IPCEIs in the context of new industrial alliances mentioned in the New Industrial Strategy for Europe.</p>
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				10. All European countries having identified, if applicable, the need for CCS/CCU as part of their strategy (producing a national CCS roadmap) for their transition towards net-zero by 2050 (included in their National Energy and Climate Plans)
WG2 CO2 Capture	Marie Bysveen (SINTEF)	Drafting 1 document describing new R&I activities and new R&I targets	6. Developing next-generation CO2 capture technologies	6. At least 3 pilots of capture technologies at TRL 7-8 in different industrial applications, including one enabling low-emission hydrogen production. At least 6 pilots of capture technologies at TRL 5-6, of which at least 2 pilots to test climate positive solutions such as Bio-CCS and direct air capture (DAC).
WG3 CO2 Storage	Filip Neele (TNO) and Jonathan Pearce (British Geological Survey)	Drafting 1 document describing new R&I activities and new R&I targets	4. Establish a European CO2 Storage Atlas 5. Unlocking European Storage capacity	5. An up-to-date and detailed inventory of the most suitable and cost-effective geological storage capacity (based on agreed methodology), identified and accepted by various national authorities in Europe.

				<p>7. An interim target of at least 6 new CO2 storage sites in preparation or operating in different settings (i.e. obtained or ready to submit an application for a storage permit). A target by 2030 of a further 9 sites to be appraised to the same level, in a range of geological settings, both onshore and offshore.</p>
WG4 CO2 Utilisation	Anastasios Perimenis (CO2 Value Europe)	Drafting 1 document describing new R&I activities and new R&I targets	7. CCU Action	<p>8. By 2030, several demonstration installations producing CO2-based fuels, chemicals and materials at the scale of tens of kt/a and contributing to EU 2030 and 2050 climate and circularity objectives.</p>

Output and timeline

The WG1 will produce **1 short document by June 2023**:

- presenting new R&I activities based on former activities 1, 2, 3, and 8; and
- presenting new R&I targets based on former targets 1, 2, 3, 4, 9, and 10.

The work should include the following elements:

- Gap analysis describing the R&I efforts required to meet the targets under the industrial carbon management strategy and the 2040 EU climate target;
- Clear link between the new R&I activities & targets and the policy objectives set under the industrial carbon management strategy and the 2040 EU climate target;
- An assessment of research efforts required to reach the policy objectives; and
- How to ensure a geographical spread of CCS projects in Europe;

The work could also include the following elements:

- Review of the number of CCS projects required for the industrial sector;
- Review of the number of CCS projects required for the power sector;
- Review of the number of PCI/PMI projects required for CO₂ transport and storage; and
- Review of national energy and climate plans;
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The number of working group meetings will be kept to a minimum. Once finalised, the document will be shared for feedback with the Technology Committee and other relevant groups.

Participants

The participants in this workstream will consist of representatives from companies active in CCS/CCU, academia, R&I organisations, public officials, and NGOs.